

Multilingualism and digital methods teaching: conceiving pedagogical materials in a multilingual-first approach

Extended abstract

Papastamkou Sofia, Lucchesi Anita, McRae Douglas

Multilingualism and DH educational resources

There has been a recent proliferation of scholarly literature regarding multilingualism in digital humanities; the tendency becoming more perceptible from 2021 on, as shown by Josh Brown (2022) or this recent call for contributions of (Viola & Spence 2022). According to Paul Spence (2021), who observed a relative shortage of theoretical debate on the implications of linguistic diversity on DH scholarship, various spaces nevertheless opened in practice for scholars to express themselves in languages other than English in recent years. Spence sees that trend, for instance, through initiatives such as the editions in Portuguese and in Spanish of the DayofDH, the releases of edited issues of the DHQ journal in Spanish, French and Portuguese in 2018 and 2020, or even the linguistic versions of Programming Historian in these three languages in addition to the original version in English.

It is in fact through practice and various degrees of community engagement that multilingual initiatives – or indeed non-English language-centered initiatives – were born in the second half of the 2010s as a result of the need for (self)training on digital methods and tools. With the exception of *The Digital Orientalist* (Lit 2015) and various networking activities on Slavic languages, these initiatives concerned the three linguistics spaces of the French-, Spanish-and Portuguese-speaking world. Up to a certain degree, these were European-led projects – such as [Ranke.2](#) or of global vocation, but essentially Western initiatives.

OpenMethods and the linguistic versions of Programming Historian (PH) are perhaps the best known among these initiatives. The former was created in 2017 (Engelhardt 2017) as "a multilingual hub and point of reference for researchers looking for existing tools that might be relevant to them" (Horvath 2021). The latter, founded in English in 2008, became a community-led methods review in 2012, and since 2016 gradually [added three linguistic subteams](#) to first launch *Programming Historian en español*, two years later *en français* and lastly *em portugês*. These two projects interact with linguistic resources in different ways. OpenMethods, on the one hand, [does not publish original contributions](#); it rather federates curated content in various languages without necessarily creating bridges between these contents, otherwise than aggregating them and diffusing them through a common website. PH, on the other hand, is principally mobilizing translations between its different linguistic versions. If, in the beginning, the non-English versions started as relays of translations of the

lessons in English, they soon began publishing original lessons: the Spanish version [did so in 2019](#), the French [in 2021](#). Also, since 2022, an interesting movement could be observed: not only was the first translation from Spanish to English published, but two more were also published from Spanish to Portuguese. No doubt this was up to a certain degree an outcome of a conscious policy of PH (Sichani et al. 2019); nevertheless, a strongly community-based project, PH is rightly considered as one of the beating hearts of digital history (Clavert & Schafer 2019), and as such it can serve as an indicator of trends in the field of Digital Humanities.

In this context, we would like to present how we consider developing a multilingual-first initiative for creating teaching materials based on Tropy for historians in three languages (Portuguese, Spanish, French), none of which is English. Tropy is an open-source, free and user-friendly tool that allows scholars to streamline the process of managing and making sense of the vast corpora of digital archival photographs that now form the basis for most historical research. With Tropy, researchers can easily add metadata to their photos, search and filter their archives based on different criteria, and analyze their collection to draw insights and connections. It also enables users to export their data in different formats and work on other platforms. Tropy is used by a large community of users and its user interface interface (UI) is available in a variety of languages, including English, German, French, Chinese, Japanese, Portuguese and Spanish, which also allows us to conceive the multilingual pedagogical materials using screenshots from its different UI's locale.

The three authors of this paper have been involved in various types of training activities for Tropy, in multiple linguistic environments. The teaching materials are meant to be developed on their firsthand experience with Tropy, as well as on their encounters with users from variegated cultural and linguistic settings. Thus, through a “collaborative” praxis (Gil and Ortega 2016), we wish to highlight work done in other languages and scientific traditions. In addition to the pedagogical approach, we would also like to present the implications such an original initiative raises for authorship, translation and datasets used for training on digital methods in history and the humanities in general.

[A multilingual-first approach: the basic idea](#)

Our oral communication during the conference in June 2023 outlined the way we had been working to draft a lesson on Tropy in a multilingual-first approach. Our specific aim was to write an online open access lesson to enable historians and other fellow humanists to gather, organize, annotate and prepare for analysis and dissemination digital photos of primary sources with Tropy software.

Why Tropy? It is quite a unique type of software as it was specifically conceived for the needs of historical research in the digital age to create order from chaos for historians literally drown in the digital representations of their sources (Takats 2017).

Furthermore, Tropy is multilingual and thus enhanced our effort to initiate a multilingual-first approach.

What we call a multilingual-first approach is a hybrid approach to conceive and author collaboratively a lesson in three languages simultaneously: Spanish, Portuguese and French. This is not about conceiving an “original” in one language that would then be replicated or adapted to the two other languages we chose, via a process of translation. Each of us being proficient in one of the three languages we chose, our approach involved first conceiving jointly a main body (a “skeleton”) around the software and its use and, second, choosing different datasets for each language that would be locally pertinent but also open to the world.

We could summarize this idea as follows:

“Our idea is to conceive the main structure of the tutorial together, and in this sense we are all co-authors of the three tutorials. Then, each one of us will be responsible (and thus be the main author) for writing it in one language: McRae for ES, Papastamkou for FR, Lucchesi for PT. Each tutorial will have adapted datasets, present a historical problem, and include references. Our datasets, however, can appeal to an international audience as well either by the type of source (for example visual) or by the ability to correspond to approaches of transnational or connected histories. In this sense, we propose three associated tutorials, in which all three can be considered as original versions.”

Our approach emanated from a need for lessons in languages other than the English, a need of which all three of us are aware of as part of our teaching and professional activities as digital historians. Moreover, our approach was enabled by the existence of multilingual infrastructures: software we can work with in multiple languages (Tropy), but also editorial relays to which it would be possible for us to have our lesson published and disseminated. Finally, our approach is also byproduct of advocacy and community engagement in favor of multilingualism.

This was as far as we had gotten when we assisted the DHBenelux 2023. By that time, we had also submitted the idea to *Programming Historian*, a multilingual journal publishing lessons on digital methods and tools for humanists.

A multilingual-first approach: from idea to praxis

The proposal was accepted by the Spanish, Portuguese and French languages editorial teams of *Programming Historian*. By the time we submit the extended abstract, the initial submissions have taken place and we are currently awaiting the peer review process.

The initial idea becoming praxis, the process turns to an interesting experiment. We all use the English language for the communications between us, both oral and written. English was also the language in which we conceived together the skeleton of the lesson. Then the skeleton served as guide for us to separately work on the version each had in our charge. On demand of the editors of *Programming Historian*, we were invited to first prepare the basis of the lesson that should be common to all three of us focusing on the software. This initial version is currently about to go through peer review and the following phase should involve corrections and integration of the

language specific elements (dataset, parts of the text where demonstrations are made using the dataset, screenshots, references). Having currently finished only the first initial version, supposedly common to the three, we are already able to observe interesting aspects of this hybrid approach.

First, we have already three originals as the so-called skeleton has been appropriated differently by each one of us. Our initial drafts are aligned but not identical or even similar. The personal style of each of us is evident in their respective version, whether it is in the way of conceiving and writing the tutorial or in which aspects the accent is put. Then, a local, understand culturally specific, dimension is already present, whether it is in the references and hyperlinks we use or in the style and conventions adopted in the writing to address the audience. Finally, the global dimension remains nevertheless present thanks to the choice of the pedagogical materials and the connected way in which the process takes place. Last but not least, the peer review process is also subject to the same exigences and is likely to necessitate specific profiles of editors and reviewers and transversal review. We wish to further give account of and analyze this hybrid approach in a more extended article.

References

Alves, Daniel, Jennifer Isasi, Sarah Melton, Sofia Papastamkou, Jessica Parr, Riva Quiroga, Nabeel Siddiqui, Brandon Walsh. 'The Programming Historian: A Global Case Study in Multilingual Open Access and DH Tutelage/Instruction' (panel), *Global Digital Humanities Symposium*, Michigan State University, East Lansing, USA, 12 April, 2021.

Brown, Josh. "Whose Language? Whose DH? Towards a taxonomy of definitional elusiveness in the digital humanities", *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 2022;, fqac072 (2022). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqac072>

Clavert, Frédéric & Valérie Schafer. « Les humanités numériques, un enjeu historique », *Quaderni*, 98 (2019). DOI : 10.4000/quaderni.1417

Engelhardt Claudia, Claudio Leone, Nicolas Larrousse, Delphine Montoliu, Yoann Moranville, Pierre Mounier, Jenny Oltersdorf, Paulin Ribbe, Ulrike Wuttke. "Open Humanities Methods Review Journal". Research Report. DARIAH, TGIR Huma-Num (UMS 3598), Göttingen State and University Library. 2017.

Gil, Alex, & Élika Ortega. "Global outlooks in digital humanities: multilingual practices and minimal computing" in Constance Crompton, Richard J. Lane and Ray Siemens (eds.), *Doing Digital Humanities*, 22-34. London: Routledge, 2016

Horvath, Alíz. "Enhancing Language Inclusivity in Digital Humanities: Towards Sensitivity and Multilingualism: Includes interviews with Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra and Cosima Wagner".

Modern Languages Open, (1), 26 (2021). DOI: <http://doi.org/10.3828/mlo.v0i0.382>

Lincoln, Matthew, Sarah Melton, Jennifer Isasi, François Dominic Laramée, 'Relocating Complexity: The Programming Historian and Multilingual Static Site Generation', *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16, 2 (2022).

Lit, L. W. C. (Eric) van. "The Digital Orientalist: Scholarship Is Becoming Bigger and Better."

MELA Notes, 88 (2015): 24–31. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43741180>.

Melton, Sarah, Joana Vieira Paulino, Nabeel Siddiqui & Riva Quiroga, 'Programming Historian: A Multilingual Open Access Publication', *Open Publishing Fest*, (17 November, 2021).

Papastamkou Sofia, Jessica Parr & Riva Quiroga. 'Challenges for Digital Literacy in the Humanities: The Open, Community-Based and Multilinguistic Approach of The Programming Historian', *NewsEye's International Conference*, Europe, 17 March, 2021.

Quiroga, Riva. 'Multilingual Digital Humanites', Digital Humanities Long View Seminar, UCLDH, UK & CESTA, USA, 10 March, 2021.

Rojas Castro, Antonio , Sofia Papastamkou, and Anna-Maria Sichani, 'Three Challenges in Developing Open Multilingual DH Educational Resources The Case of The Programming Historian', *DH 2019 Conference*, ADHO, Utrecht, Netherlands (8 July 2019) <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-02277639>

Sichani, Anna-Maria, James Baker, Maria José Afanador Llach, and Brandon Walsh. "Diversity and Inclusion in Digital Scholarship and Pedagogy: The Case of the Programming Historian". *Insights: The UKSG Journal* 32 (1): 16 (2019). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.465>

Spence, Paul J. & R. Brandao (2021). "Towards Language Sensitivity and Diversity in the Digital Humanities", *Digital Studies / Le champ numérique* 11(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.8098>

Takats, Sean "Tropy", Blogpost, *Quintessence of Ham*, 26 October 2017, <http://quintessenceofham.org/2017/10/26/tropy>

Viola, Lorella & Paul Spence (2021). "CfP - Chapters solicited for an edited volume on "Multilingual DH"", <https://www.c2dh.uni.lu>, <https://www.c2dh.uni.lu/news/cfp-chapters-solicited-edited-volume-multilingual-dh>

Suggested reviewersⁱ

Anna Maria Sichani

Riva Quiroga

Paul Spence <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/people/paul-spence>

ⁱ Please note that the first two suggested persons are members of Programming Historian and so is one of the authors (Sofia Papastamkou), in case this might be considered as conflict of interest. Neither Sichani nor Quiroga are involved in the editorial process of the lessons currently in progress. Their contact details can be found at: <https://programminghistorian.org/en/project-team>